

Impact of Curtailment of Renewable Energies Sources on High Voltage Network Expansion Planning

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Abstract—Due to the increasing share of renewable energy sources (RES), electrical networks need to be continuously expanded to integrate all RES without violating operational constraints. In the conventional network expansion process only new grid assets such as lines and transformers are considered to resolve congestions. Due to the volatile feed-in of RES, some assets might only be necessary for a few critical situations each year. Hence, a curtailment of feed-in from RES in critical situations is being discussed in order to reduce the required network expansion measures. Nowadays in Europe neither a common allowance for planning a network considering RES curtailment nor an indication of costs for the use of curtailment exist. Therefore, this paper investigates the impact of RES curtailment on the planning of high voltage distribution networks.

Index Terms—Network planning, curtailment, flexibility, renewable energies, RES

I. INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

In recent years, the installed generation capacity of RES has been increasing rapidly in many regions in Germany. Especially the distribution networks including the low- and medium-voltage level and the high voltage subtransmission networks have to cope with great changes in their network usage [1]. Historically, these networks have been designed to distribute the electric energy generated in large generation units connected to the transmission system to the loads connected to the distribution network. Therefore, the network planning process used a network planning case (NPC) describing the critical load conditions to dimension the network. With the increasing generation capacity installed in these networks, the critical situations can nowadays be caused by a high RES feed-in. In order to host the newly installed generation capacity, a lot of networks need to be expanded. In order to do so, additional NPCs representing these critical feed-in situations are included in the planning process. In the conventional planning process, the identified congestions in the network are resolved by adding new or reinforcing existing assets such as overhead lines, cables or transformers. Following this procedure to host the full generation capacity in all critical feed-in situations may lead to many assets being

highly loaded only for a very limited time throughout the year as the feed-in of RES is highly volatile and peaks a rather rare. This raises the question, whether expanding the network to host the full capacity is the cost-optimal solution for solving congestions in the network as the curtailment of RES feed-in in critical situations offers an alternative option.

Nowadays curtailment is only applied in emergency situations, to ensure system stability [2]. The network planner however has to dimension the networks to host the full capacity. Currently, it is being discussed to consider the curtailment within the planning process in order to reduce the overall costs of network expansion and operation [3]. While reducing network expansion costs, additional costs for the curtailment procedure may arise. On the one hand the costs for the replacement of the curtailed energy have to be considered. Furthermore, the information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure needed to coordinate the curtailment during network operation has to be installed and maintained.

The novel aspect of considering RES curtailment in the network planning stage is investigated in this paper. Therefore, a network planning algorithm based on a constructive heuristic is combined with a security constraint optimal power flow (SCOPF) algorithm determining the required RES curtailment. For each network expansion step the curtailed energy is determined in order to find an optimal solution for the combination of conventional expansion measures and the use of operational flexibilities based on a technical and economical evaluation of the investigated networks.

II. ANALYSIS AND MODEL

A. RES Curtailment Strategies in Distribution Networks

In case of congestions in a network due to a high feed-in of RES, technical constraints regarding operational voltages and currents may require a curtailment of the power feed-in. According to current regulations, the curtailment of RES is so far only applied in emergency situations, to ensure a secure

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operation of the system [2]. In this case the generation units which have the technical ability to be controlled and which have the biggest effect on the congestions are curtailed.

To consider a curtailment within the planning process, different strategies are being discussed. In the “fixed curtailment” approach, a maximum power feed-in for each generation unit regardless of the current network state is defined. This approach allows an easy implementation in network operation, as the curtailment is implemented decentral within the generation units, requiring no communication system. However this approach may lead to a high amount of curtailed energy in non-critical situations. The fixed curtailment is exemplarily visualized in Figure 1 showing the duration curve of a single PV-unit. Reducing the maximum power feed in to 60% of the nominal power results in a loss of approximately 2.5% of the annual energy feed-in.

Figure 1. Exemplary duration curve for a single PV generation unit with a fixed feed-in curtailment

Another strategy called “dynamic curtailment” only curtails the feed-in from generation units with a significant influence on the congested elements and only does so in critical situations. While significantly reducing the amount of curtailed energy, this strategy requires an ICT system to implement the curtailment which may lead to additional investment and operational costs. Furthermore this implementation makes a more detailed simulation of the network operation in the planning process indispensable. In this paper, the dynamic curtailment approach is used to determine the curtailed energy within the simulation of the network operation.

B. General Description of the Network Planning Problem

In the considered network planning problem, the task is to find an optimal combination between network expansion measures and the use of operational flexibilities in the form of RES curtailment to resolve critical situations in the network caused by an increasing feed-in from RES. In this case the costs resulting caused by the curtailment have to be included in the planning problem.

As different network configurations may fulfill all technical requirements usually a cost evaluation is performed in order to choose the best network configuration based on economic criteria. Therefore, the network is economically optimized while fulfilling all technical constraints.

In the following sections, the formulated network planning problem is analyzed in terms of the degrees of freedom and in terms of the technical constraints to be maintained in network operation. Furthermore, the economic factors to be considered in the cost evaluation are introduced.

1) Degrees of Freedom

Within the network planning problem, the supply task including capacity and location of all loads, generators and all connection points to the transmission system is assumed to be given. Hence, the positioning of stations is not part of the optimization problem. In addition, the nominal voltage for each busbar is assumed to be fixed. The resulting degrees of freedom within the planning task are either enforcing existing network assets or adding new assets to the network. The considered assets include overhead lines, cables, transformers and shunt compensation elements.

Cables and Overhead Lines

For each route connecting two stations of the network, the number of branches and the type of each branch has to be determined. For a given set of routes Ω_R , the branches to be realized on each route $r \in \Omega_R$ have to be optimized. The maximum number of branches per route $B_r = \{b_{r,1}; b_{r,2}; \dots; b_{r,n}\}$ can be limited to $|B_r| \leq c_r$ and for each route restrictions whether branches have to be realized as cables or overhead lines can be formulated. Within the formulation of the optimization problem, each possible branch is a degree of freedom that can be chosen to:

- No realization of the branch: $b_{r,i} = 0$
- Realization as cable of type t_c : $b_{r,i} = t_c$
- Realization as overhead line of type t_l : $b_{r,i} = t_l$

Transformers

For each station either connecting the considered network with the transmission system or connecting two different voltage levels within the optimized network area, the number and type of transformers is a degree of freedom.

For a given set of stations Ω_S , the transformers to be realized in each station $s \in \Omega_S$ have to be optimized. For each station the maximum number of transformers $T_s = \{t_{s,1}; t_{s,2}; \dots; t_{s,n}\}$ can be limited to $|T_s| \leq c_s$. Within the formulation of the optimization problem, each possible transformer is a degree of freedom that can be chosen to:

- No realization of the transformer: $t_{s,i} = 0$
- Realization with type t_t : $t_{s,i} = t_t$

Shunt Compensations Elements

In order to resolve critical voltages in the network, shunt compensations elements can be installed within each station. In case of over voltages reactor coils and in case of under voltages capacitor banks are used to provide the required reactive power. The amount of inductive and capacitive compensation elements at each station is a further degree of freedom.

Operational Degrees of Freedom

Considering the operational use of flexibilities within the planning stage of the network offers an additional degree of freedom. As this work focuses on dynamic RES curtailment as a flexibility option, the amount of curtailed power feed-in ΔP_g^{npc} for each considered network planning case npc and for each generator g is an additional degree of freedom. The amount of feed-in that can be reduced for each generator is limited by its minimum and maximum feed-in in each NPC.

$$P_{g,min}^{npc} \leq P_g^{npc} - \Delta P_g^{npc} \leq P_{g,max}^{npc} \quad (1)$$

The maximum feed-in usually is based on the availability of the volatile renewable energy source ($P_{g,max}^{npc} = P_g^{npc}$) while the lower limit $P_{g,min}^{npc}$ is either zero or limited by operational limits of the generation unit.

2) Technical Constraints

To prevent damages of the assets, operational constraints for the branch current I_b are defined for each branch in the system. The branch current has to stay below this limit during the network operation.

$$I_b^{npc} \leq I_b^{max} \quad (2)$$

The maximum current I_b^{max} can either refer to the Permanent Admissible Transmission Loading (PATL) or the Temporary Admissible Transmission Loading (TATL) allowing for a temporary overloading of the lines, if short term operational measures such as switching actions or the use of curtailment can resolve the overloading [4].

In this paper I_b^{max} refers to the PATL value within the evaluation of the network without contingencies and to the TATL value in contingency situations.

To ensure a stable voltage supply for customers and to prevent damages of assets due to over or under voltages, the nodal voltage V_n has to stay within operational limits [5].

$$V_n^{min} \leq V_n^{npc} \leq V_n^{max} \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, it has to be ensured that the minimum and maximum short circuit currents stay within the operational constraints. The upper limit is due to the thermal and mechanical dimensioning of the assets and the switching capability of the short circuit breakers, while the lower limit is needed for a reliable detection of faults.

In meshed high voltage networks serving a large number of customers, a reliable and uninterrupted supply is another important aspect. In order to achieve a high reliability, usually the (n-1)-criteria is applied to ensure that all customers can still be supplied even after the outage of one line or transformer. Therefore, the technical constraints (2) and (3) have to be fulfilled in all (n-1)-contingency situations. In medium voltage networks an outage after a failure is allowed, but the load has to be reconnected after switching measures.

To assess the ability of a network configuration to ensure an operation within all technical constraints, power flow calculations and (n-1)-contingency analyses have to be performed for all critical NPCs in the planning process. In order to evaluate the dynamic curtailment of RES in critical situations a further determination of the required energy curtailment has to be performed.

3) Economical Assessment of Network Configurations

Within the planning process different network configurations fulfilling all technical requirements may be identified. Based on a cost evaluation, the configurations resulting in the least overall costs should be preferred based on economic criteria.

In order to adequately compare all occurring costs for the construction and the operation of the network, the annuity method is a commonly applied technique to convert single investments to average annual payments. Expenses for the operation of the network, e.g. network losses, are calculated on an annual basis and do not have to be converted.

The annual capital expenditures \dot{C}_{capex} are calculated based on the investment costs $C_{invest,a}$ for each asset a , the costs for installing the asset $C_{install,a}$ in the network and the annuity factor \dot{a}_a . They can be calculated using (4).

$$\dot{C}_{capex} = \sum_{a \in Assets} \dot{a}_a \cdot (C_{invest,a} + C_{install,a}) \quad (4)$$

In the planning phase, the annual operational costs accounting for operation- and maintenance of the assets $\dot{C}_{opex,assets}$ are estimated based on an operational cost factor \dot{b}_a as a percentage of the investment costs (5).

$$\dot{C}_{opex,assets} = \sum_{a \in Assets} (\dot{b}_a \cdot C_{invest,a}) \quad (5)$$

The annual costs for losses \dot{C}_{loss} can be estimated based on the NPCs used in the planning process. Therefore, the energy E_{loss} to cover the network losses within each NPC is weighted using a factor r_l relating each NPC to the percentage of its contribution to the annual energy needed to cover the losses. The annual costs are then calculated using the specific energy costs $C_{E,loss}$ (6).

$$\dot{C}_{loss} = \frac{C_{E,loss}}{1\alpha} \cdot \sum_{npc \in NPCs} (r_{l,npc} \cdot E_{loss,npc}) \quad (6)$$

Due to the consideration of RES curtailment within the planning process, the annual curtailment costs \hat{C}_{cur} have to be included in the economic evaluation. These costs are calculated based on the annual amount of energy curtailed. The determination of this energy is based on the curtailed energy $E_{cur,g}^{npc}$ of each generator g in each NPC. The curtailed energy is weighted with the factor r_c relating the NPC to the percentage of its contribution to the annual curtailed energy. The annual energy costs are then calculated based on the specific energy costs $c_{E,cur}$ (7).

$$\hat{C}_{cur} = \frac{c_{E,cur}}{1a} \cdot \sum_{npc \in NPCs} (r_{f,npc} \cdot \sum_{g \in Gen} E_{cur,g}^{npc}) \quad (7)$$

Based on these considerations, the overall annual network costs \hat{C}_{ntw} can be calculated using (8).

$$\hat{C}_{ntw} = \hat{C}_{capex} + \hat{C}_{opex,assets} + \hat{C}_{loss} + \hat{C}_{cur} \quad (8)$$

Using these definitions the annual expenses for building and operating the network can be evaluated based on the network expansion measures chosen within a network configuration as well as on the resulting system losses and the curtailed energy.

4) Choice of Optimization Algorithm

The presented network planning problem describes a mixed-integer, nonlinear optimization problem. The combinatorial problem of choosing a set of new network assets is a mixed integer problem. Furthermore the constraints and the objective function based on the network costs are nonlinear as they are based on the power flow equations and the amount curtailed energy. As described in literature, mathematical methods are able to solve comparable optimization problems, but require non acceptable computational effort for large scale realistic networks [7]. On the other hand (meta)-heuristic algorithms have proven to find good, but not necessarily optimal, solutions for network planning problems in reasonable computation time [8],[9]. For this reason, a heuristic method to solve the given planning problem will be introduced in the following section.

III. METHODOLOGY

The implemented network planning algorithm combines a heuristic approach identifying the optimal network expansion measures based on congestions in the network with an iterative-linear SCOPF to simulate the curtailment for each NPC.

A. Overall Methodology

In order to analyze the impact of considering curtailment within the planning process, an iterative approach performing a stepwise expansion of the network has been implemented. Within each iteration the network is expanded using the expansion measure having the greatest influence on remaining congestions in the network. After each expansion step the

required amount of curtailed energy to stay within all operational constraints is determined using a SCOPF algorithm. The overall methodology is visualized in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overview of the overall methodology

As stated in (8) the objective function of the optimization problem is solely based on minimizing the overall annual costs for enforcing and operating the network. The objective value is calculated based on the expansion measures in the evaluated network configuration and on the results of the technical evaluation for each NPC. The heuristic algorithm determining the expansion measures combined with the technical evaluation and the curtailment ensure the compliance with all technical constraints.

B. Constructive Heuristic for the Determination of Network Expansion Measures

In order to modify the network structure stepwise according to the available degrees of freedom a constructive heuristic is used to determine the next expansion measure to be performed. As combinations of different expansion measures and the removal of existing assets is not considered within the heuristic approach, it is not guaranteed to find an optimal set of network expansion measures. However, constructive heuristics have shown good results comparable to other optimization algorithms such as genetic algorithms applied to network planning problems [9],[10].

The heuristic algorithm starts by using the existing network to fulfill a given supply task and iteratively expands the network until no congestion remains. Each NPC defined for the dimensioning of the network is applied to identify congestions in the network based on overloaded branches (lines and transformers) or nodes with voltage problems. The heuristic expansion method for meshed network structures

commonly found in high voltage networks is based on sensitivity indices SI which are used for the identification of the next asset to be added to the network.

For all branches, the sensitivity index $SI_{T,b}$ is calculated using the percentage of thermal overloading ΔI_b^{npc} of assets for each npc in base case (n-0) and in the most critical contingency situation c out of all contingencies C considered in the (n-1)-analysis.

$$\Delta I_{b,(n-0)}^{npc} = \max \left\{ 0; \frac{I_b^{npc}}{I_{r,b}} - 1 \right\} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta I_{b,(n-1)}^{npc} = \max \left\{ 0; \max_{c \in C} \left\{ \frac{I_b^{c,npc}}{I_{r,b}} - 1 \right\} \right\} \quad (10)$$

Based on these parameters the sensitivity indices $SI_{T,b}$ can be calculated for each branch considering the most critical situation for the branch and the annual costs to resolve this congestion.

$$SI_{T,b} = \frac{1\text{€}/a}{\dot{c}_{capex,b}} \cdot \max_{npc \in NPC_s} \left\{ \Delta I_{b,(n-0)}^{npc} + \Delta I_{b,(n-1)}^{npc} \right\} \quad (11)$$

The route or station containing the branch with the highest SI_T value is expanded by adding an additional line or transformer of the same type in parallel to the congested element.

In case the congestions are due to voltage problems a further sensitivity indices for the voltage SI_V is determined. The minimum and maximum percentage of over and under voltage occurring in base and contingency situations are determined for each node n . The calculation for over voltages is formulated in (12) and (13).

$$\Delta VO_{n,(n-0)}^{npc} = \max \left\{ 0; \frac{V_n^{npc} - V_n^{max}}{V_{n,0}} \right\} \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta VO_{n,(n-1)}^{npc} = \max \left\{ 0; \max_{c \in C} \left\{ \frac{V_n^{c,npc} - V_n^{max}}{V_{n,0}} \right\} \right\} \quad (13)$$

The sensitivity index for the overvoltage $SI_{VO,n}$ is

$$SI_{VO,n} = \max_{n \in NPC-D} \left\{ \Delta VO_{(n-0),i,n} + \Delta VO_{(n-1),i,n} \right\} \quad (14)$$

The indices for under voltages ΔVU_n^{npc} and $SI_{VU,n}$ are calculated in an analogue way. The overall value SI_V is determined using (15).

$$SI_{V,n} = \max \left\{ SI_{VO,n}; SI_{VU,n} \right\} \quad (15)$$

If voltage problems remain, the station with the highest SI_V index is chosen to add additional shunt compensation elements.

Using this heuristic, the network is expanded step by step reinforcing the most critical parts of the network until no curtailment is necessary during network operation. After each

expansion step, the network configuration is updated and the technical and economical evaluation including the simulation of the curtailment are performed.

C. Simulation of RES Curtailment

The curtailed amount of energy to reach a system state without violations of technical constraints is determined for each NPC using a SCOPF algorithm. The applied algorithm has been developed and tested for large scale meshed networks and is able to include (n-1)-contingency situations in the optimization process ensuring an active or passive (n-1)-secure network state [11]. The general calculation process is visualized in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Overview of the SCOPF algorithm

The SCOPF formulation is based on an iterative linear optimization using the jacobian matrix of the system and the current system state to obtain linear sensitivities in order to estimate the influence of changes in the power feed-in per node to all nodal voltages in the system and thus on the power flows over all branches. Starting from an initial power flow calculation and a linearized approximation of the effects of contingency situations, a linear optimization problem is formulated to optimize the use of flexibilities. The objective function of the optimization problem includes penalty cost terms for remaining violations of technical constraints and cost terms for the use of flexibilities. In an iterative approach, a new power flow calculation based on the updated use of flexibilities after each linear optimization step is used to recalculate the sensitivities and thus update the linear optimization problem accounting for the nonlinearity of the problem. This procedure is continued until a convergent solution is found. A complete formulation of the applied SCOPF can be found in [11].

The outcomes of the SCOPF are the system state before and after an optimized use of flexibilities including all violation of technical constraints needed to calculate the beforehand introduced sensitivity indices. Furthermore, the use of curtailment as the only considered flexibility options within each NPC is calculated for each node containing RES feed-in in the system.

IV. TEST CASE

The presented methodology is used for the expansion planning of a high voltage subtransmission network. In order to determine the curtailed energy more exactly, a simulation of the network operation for selected network configurations is performed considering time series of 8760 hourly values. To analyze the interaction between network expansion measures and RES curtailment, a stepwise simulation realizing subsets of the identified expansion measures is performed and the curtailed energy is determined. Furthermore the optimization is performed for two different cost assumptions for the specific energy costs in order to quantify the impact of different curtailment costs.

A. Scenario and Assumptions

The calculations are performed for a real high voltage system consisting of meshed 110 kV and 30 kV circuits [12]. A description of the existing network can be found in Table I.

TABLE I. EXISTING NETWORK DESCRIPTION

Existing HV Network	30 kV	110 kV
Stations	27	63
Overhead Lines	69 km	840 km
Cables	208 km	4 km
110kV/30kV transformer	25	
30kV/10kV transformer	55	57
110kV/10kV transformer		

The load and generation connected to the system in the present situation and in the future scenario is presented in Table II. The load connect to the system is expected to remain unchanged while the total generation capacity of 915 MW connected to the system today is increased by 85% to 1697 MW [12].

TABLE II. LOAD AND GENERATION SCENARIOS

Load and Generation	Present Situation	Future Scenario
Installed Load	1306 MW	1306 MW
PV generation capacity	444 MW	696 MW
Wind generation capacity	362 MW	871 MW
Biomass generation capacity	109 MW	130 MW

The economic evaluation for all lines and transformers includes the costs for required circuit breakers and switchgear. For cables, also the costs for cable trenches are included. Costs for busbars are not part of the optimization and do not change between the examined networks. The interest rate used in the annuity method is set to 5.5%. The cost assumptions for all assets taken from [13] are summarized in Table III.

TABLE III. COST ASSUMPTIONS

Assets		Assumptions		
Type	Nominal voltage	Invest. costs	Operational costs	Life time
Overhead Line	30 kV	80	2	40
	110 kV	400		
Cable	30 kV	80	1	
	110 kV	800		
Transformer	110 kV/30 kV	1000	2	30

For the curtailment of RES only volatile PV- and wind-generation units are considered while the generation from biomass has not been curtailed.

B. Results

In order to analyze the results for different stages in the network expansion process, the result of the conventional planning solution, without curtailing RES feed-in has been determined and is described in the following as "100% expansion plan". To analyze different stages in the network expansion process, the amount of expansion measures is varied between no expansion (0% expansion plan) and the 100% expansion plan. To simulate these steps in the expansion process, identified measures are carried out step by step until the given percentage of the annual network expansion costs are reached. As the load does not increase but only the generation capacity rises, it is always possible to achieve a secure network state by curtailing RES as the existing network had been dimensioned for the load. The results of a sensitivity analysis for the specific energy costs $c_{E,cur}$ of 35 €/MWh and 100 €/MWh are shown in Figure 4. The cost of 35 €/MWh was the average spot price in the period between September 2014 and August 2015 at the electricity spot market EEX. The costs of 100 €/MWh have been used in recent studies like [13] with respect to the current feed-in tariff of RES in Germany.

Figure 4. Comparison of different specific energy costs on the results

The complete expansion of the network to host the full RES capacity results in annual network expansion costs of 12.6 million €/a. With specific energy costs of 100 €/MWh the total annual costs are the lowest for the 50% expansion plan. In this case the annual costs for expansion measures result in 6.1 million €/a and the curtailment costs are 3.1 million €/a. This is a cost reduction of about 27% compared to the full network expansion. It has to be mentioned, that this offset has to be used to cover the ICT installation costs in order to control the curtailment which may alter the identified optimum. It can also be stated that the total costs increase significantly, when no sufficient expansion measures are carried out. In the case without network expansion the total costs of 21.7 million €/a almost double compared to the fully expanded network. Reducing the specific energy costs to 35 €/MWh makes solutions with less network expansion more attractive. For the 50% expansion plan, the total costs reduce to 7.1 million €/a which is a cost reduction of 43% in comparison to full network expansion. In this case even the solutions without network expansion and with 25% network expansion lead to similar costs as the 50% expansion plan. In these cases only the share of curtailment and network expansion costs differ.

For each analyzed step of the expansion plan the yearly curtailed energy has been calculated and is presented in Figure 5. In case of no expansion the curtailment of wind energy is about 12% of the yearly energy feed-in, whereas for photovoltaic energy roughly 8% is curtailed. It can be seen, that the first expansion measures added to the network from 0% to 25% and from 25% to 50% show the highest impact on the curtailed energy, while the expansion from 50% to 75%

and from 75% to 100% only lead to a small decrease of curtailed energy for the same additional amount of annual network expansion costs.

Figure 5. Aggregated annual energy curtailment for wind and PV generation

In the following, the cost-minimal 50% expansion plan is further analyzed. From 90 substations in the network, at only 27 a curtailment is necessary during the simulation. At some substations only a negligible amount of energy is curtailed while the most congested substation still reaches an annual energy curtailment of 21%. This leads to the conclusion that in case a maximum annual curtailment per substation or per generation unit is desired, more network expansion measures have to be carried out in order to fulfill this requirement. Furthermore, the prioritization of the expansion measures within the expansion plan might change due to this additional restriction.

Figure 6. Curtailment duration curve for the 50% expansion plan

In Figure 6 the curtailment duration curve for the 50% expansion plan aggregated over the whole network is shown. It can be seen that for about 1000 hours a curtailment of RES is necessary. In critical hours a curtailment of up to 140 MWh/h for PV and 120 MWh/h for wind is required. The maximum combined curtailment reaches 215 MWh/h in the most critical hour.

This most critical hour in the network has been further analyzed. Figure 7 shows the curtailed energy of the different wind and PV units in the network. The area with the highest

curtailment is in the northeast of the network, where several wind and PV units have to be curtailed in order to avoid the overloading of network assets which results in total a curtailment of 215 MWh/h.

Figure 7. Curtailment and line loadings in the most critical hour for the 50% expansion plan

V. CONCLUSIONS

In order to host the increasing share of decentralized renewable energy sources, distribution networks need to be expanded. Due to the volatile feed-in of RES many new network assets are only necessary for a few critical situations, but lead to huge investments. Therefore, the consideration of RES curtailment in critical situations is discussed to be included in the planning stage. This could result in a reduction of expansion costs, but on the other hand leads to additional costs for the replacement of the curtailed energy and ICT systems required to coordinate the power output of the RES units. This paper introduced a new approach of finding an optimal compromise between network expansion and curtailment of RES. A constructive heuristic to find an optimal expansion plan has been combined with a simulation of the network operation. The method has been tested on a real high voltage subtransmission network for a future scenario with high RES penetration. It can be seen that with a decreasing price for curtailed energy less reinforcement of the network becomes more attractive. Nevertheless, even with high specific costs of 100 €/MWh for the curtailed energy, a reinforcement of roughly 50% of all necessary reinforcement measures seems to be cost optimal. The cost reduction achieved in this case is about 27% compared to a full expansion of the network. This cost reduction can be used to cover the ICT costs for the coordination of the RES units. As a

dynamic curtailment has been applied, it can be seen that some units experience a very high curtailment of up to 21% of their yearly energy production, whereas other do not have to be curtailed at all. In total the curtailment of RES shows a high impact on the overall costs of network expansion and operation.

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